

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Duration: 40 months

Report on **Milestone MS24**

Implementation of standard Dataverse installation on EOSC (Standard installation of repository service online)

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Milestone	30/04/2019
Actual Achievement Date	09/07/2019
Lead Beneficiary/LTP	7. KNAW (DANS)
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Task	5.2
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Abstract:

This document reports of Milestone MS24, Implementation of standard Dataverse installation on the Google cloud of CESSDA ERIC. This installation will be used to implement developed functionalities during the SSHOC project.

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1. Introduction

Task 5.2 of the SSHOC project will develop a repository services for institutes (of CESSDA, DARIAH, CLARIN, E-RIHS) running centrally on cloud platforms or to download as a 'archive in a box' solution for individual institutes. These services will provide SSH institutions without a data repository service, such a facility for their designated communities. For institutes with limited technical resources, the service offers an opportunity to simply and effectively create an online repository. For institutes, which already provide archival solutions, this service can be used to set up a sharing and self-depositing environment for researchers in a user-centric manner.

The new service will be built upon the Dataverse software. It has a modular design principle using API's, that allow for distributed file storage, and supports the building of further micro-services on top. Additional functionality will be developed to meet the needs of the European SSH community.

To implement and test the additional functionality implementation of a standard Dataverse installation on a Google cloud platform is needed. For this purpose, we use the CESSDA google cloud. This milestone reports of this installation.

2. Description of the Milestone

The SSHOC Dataverse development installation is implemented as a continuous integration pipeline, it **runs on Jenkins in the CESSDA ERIC cloud** and allows to build all Docker images and to automatically deploy all Dataverse components like database, search engine and the application itself.

Installation is available at <https://dataverse-sshoc-staging.cessda.eu/> (username / password: "cessda" / "CESSDA2018").

Source code is available at: <https://bitbucket.org/account/user/cessda/projects/DVS> (and <https://github.com/Dans-labs/dataverse-kubernetes>).

2.1. Role of the Milestone

This installation will be used to implement and test the additional functionality that will be developed during the SSHOC project to the needs of the CESSDA, DARIAH, CLARIN, E-RIHS communities.

2.2. Means of verification

Installation is available at <https://dataverse-sshoc-staging.cessda.eu/> (username / password: "cessda" / "CESSDA2018").

Source code is available at: <https://bitbucket.org/account/user/cessda/projects/DVS> (and <https://github.com/Dans-labs/dataverse-kubernetes>)

2.3. Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

There was a delay of 2 months because the arrangement of the Jenkins pipeline took more time than foreseen.

3. Conclusions and next steps

Project is on track. Extra functionality which will be developed during the SSHOC project will be deployed on the SSHOC Dataverse development server.